

Filipino Teacher Foreign Language Fluency Anxiety in the United States

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Lea Ann A. Apura

Faculty Member, Page Middle School- Page Unified School District Page, Arizona, USA, 86040
apuraleaann@gmail.com

Abstract

The descriptive correlational study examines 50 Filipino teachers' foreign language fluency anxiety levels in the US for school year 2021-2022 and how socio-demographic factors affect performance. This use a modified 30-item questionnaire from the standardized questionnaire on Foreign Language Teaching Anxiety by Selami Aydin and Ozgehan Ustuk (2020). Mean interpretation, frequency and percentage distribution, and ANOVA were used to treat the data. Female educators aged 31–35, mostly teachers, dominated the study. These teachers had one year of experience and earned 100,000–200,000 per month. This study found that Filipino teachers have variable foreign language fluency anxiety levels. Teachers were anxious about making mistakes and meeting new students when assessing their language proficiency. Results found that teaching inexperience increased stress when students did not participate in class discussions. The research also shows that student disinterest intensifies foreign language fluency anxiety, with many teachers disappointed by negative student behavior. Teachers typically experience stress when unprepared for class and lack the materials or planning to prepare for discussions, contributing to stress. The study also found age-related relationships between language proficiency self-perception and time difficulties with management. While their positions greatly influenced their self-perception of language proficiency, language barriers differed by duration of service and time difficulties with management. These findings demonstrate the complexity of foreign language fluency anxiety among Filipino US instructors and the need to overcome it to improve their teaching through targeted interventions, seeking mentorship and joining professional development programs.

Key Words: Foreign Language Anxiety, English Proficiency, Teacher Migration, English as Second and Foreign Language

Introduction

Language is the most important part of good education because it is the main way information is shared, ideas are discussed, and understanding is built in the classroom" (Smith, 2020). Imberti (2017) says that it gives people a place to talk about their feelings, explain their points of view, tell stories, and share complex ideas and information. Also, language is a symbolic tool that lets us share information and plays a key role in setting up social structures that help us feel more like ourselves and like a group in the classroom (Imberti, 2017).

Nevertheless, Filipino teachers go on a trip to the United States to participate in professional activities, learn new things, and pursuit better opportunity. These educators are made up of people who have immigrated, moved, had international training, trained overseas, come from minority immigrant groups, do not speak English as their first language, or were born overseas (Bense, 2016). Teachers who move to other countries need help adapting to the language. Thus, teachers must deal with five specific challenges to improve their speaking skills as communicators and fit in well in a foreign environment. Teachers' common challenges are language proficiency, a lack of previous teaching experience, getting students interested, fear of negative evaluations, and limited time. According to Mercer and Gregersen 2020, research shows that language barriers in educational situations can make people feel different things. These feelings include bad ones, like anger, frustration, sadness, and worry, and good ones, like happiness, excitement, surprise, and joy.

Teachers need help to become linguistically competent in their new environment to communicate their instruction, especially since cultural and procedural dynamics in the educational system are changing, especially in foreign countries (Teacher Dialogue, 2022). The main thing that makes it hard for new teachers to get used to their work setting is that they have to get used to the language they use and the context in which they talk to their coworkers and teach their students. These interconnected parts are the main focus of our study because they have a lot to do with how well teachers abroad do in the United States. Thus, the study examines 50 Filipino teachers' foreign language fluency anxiety levels in the US for school year 2021-2022 and how socio-demographic factors affect performance. The study's finding were used to develop proposed professional development trainings for Filipino teachers teaching in the US.

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework and Objectives of the Study

The descriptive correlational study examines 50 Filipino teachers' foreign language fluency anxiety levels in the US for school year 2021-2022 and how socio-demographic factors affect performance. This research focus is very

relevant to US embassy to use instructor’s level of linguistic competence for evaluating applicants. More so, this will help school administration to create a program addressing various cultural assortments. For immigrant teachers to gain information about cultural differences to help them to understand different behavioral and cultural backgrounds. For school district to consider the varied cultural beliefs, traditions, and behaviors of the teachers. Lastly, for the future researchers to gain information for comparison of their study findings. Findings of this study will develop proposed professional development programs for Filipino teachers teaching in the US to strengthen their English language fluency and proficiency, addressing anticipated stress when teaching in a new culture and environment, time management, and interactive teaching approaches for US students.

The study was inspired by the sociocultural theory of Lev Vygotsky (1896-1934). According to this idea, thinking is more than a psychological process. Instead, it is a process affected by things and actions that are part of the culture. Vygotsky also believed that language affects learning. Vygotsky thought that social structures affect how people work and connect, affecting how they think, believe, act, and see the world (Miller, 2021). Therefore, the concept of cultural adaptation must have something to do with how individuals interact and change when they move to a new place. This study aimed to determine how a teacher's age, gender, job, highest level of schooling, number of years of work, and monthly income affect their ability to adapt to American culture. Also, the study identifies the dependent variables and plans to look into this teacher's foreign language barriers and fluency anxiety in terms of how she sees her language skills, her lack of teaching experience, her students' lack of interest, her fear of receiving a negative evaluation, and her trouble managing her time.

Methodology

This descriptive correlational research study used the snowball or referral sampling approach to select the 50 Filipino teacher respondents and the study was conducted across various public school districts throughout the United States that includes selected public school districts from 5 different states, Minnesota, Nevada, Arizona, New Mexico, and Alaska. By including teachers from various schools in different states, the study aimed to capture diverse perspectives and experiences among Filipino educator respondents. The study used a modified 30-item questionnaire from the standardized questionnaire on Foreign Language Teaching Anxiety by Selami Aydin and Ozgehan Ustuk (2020). The instrument was validated by three 3 experts using the criteria by Carter V. Good and Douglas E. Scates. The total validation mean score was 3.8 and interpreted a very good and valid to administer. For the questionnaire’s reliability check, the test was administered to the Filipino teachers who have the exact characteristics in the nearest school but are not the study’s respondents. The score subjected to the reliability test using the Cronbach’s Alpha with a value of 0.83 that tells the questionnaire was reliable.

The questionnaire is divided into two main parts. Part I collects demographic information about the respondents and Part II is about the teacher foreign language fluency anxiety that was divided into 5 categories of questions, such as self-perception of language proficiency, teaching inexperience, lack of student interest, fear of negative evaluation , and difficulties with time management. Each category focuses on specific aspects of language fluency anxiety and related teaching challenges. The questionnaire primarily uses a 5-point Likert scale as 5-strongly agree to 1- strongly disagree that provides a quantifiable measure of respondent’s perceptions and feelings.

Aside from the data retrieved from the questionnaire, the researcher conducted a Key Informant Interviews to make a meaningful support with the quantitative data. The participants answer qualitative questions based on relevant expertise and insight on the topic and to explain concerns that require more explanation. The data were subjected to appropriate statistical treatments in order to answer the identified problems under study. Frequency and percentage distribution, ANOVA, and the mean with interpretation below were used to treat, evaluate and interpret the data.

FOREIGN LANGUAGE FLUENCY ANXIETY	Interpretation
1.00 – 1.49	No Anxiety
1.50 – 2.49	Low Anxiety
2.50 – 3.49	Moderate Anxiety
3.50 – 4.49	High Anxiety
4.50 – 5.00	Extreme Anxiety

Results and Discussion

The Socio-demographic of Teacher Teaching in the United States.

This section represents the six socio-demographic profiles of US Filipino teachers regarding sex, age, position, length of service, monthly income, and highest educational attainment. The table below shows the distribution of the Filipino teachers teaching in the United States.

Table 1. The socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, position, length of service, monthly income, and high educational attainment

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	10	20.0%
Female	40	80.0%
Age		
20-25 years old	3	6.0%
26-30 years old	15	30.0%
31-35 years old	17	34.0%
36-40 years old	4	8.0%
over 40 years old	11	22.0%
Position		
Teacher	19	38.00%
Special Education Teacher	6	12.00%
High School Teacher	3	6.00%
ELA Teacher	2	4.00%
ELEM. TEACHER	2	4.00%
ESS Teacher	2	4.00%
High School FACS Teacher	2	4.00%
Math Teacher	2	4.00%
Middle School Teacher	2	4.00%
Science Teacher	2	4.00%
6th Grade ELA	1	2.00%
7th Grade Resource Teacher	1	2.00%
English Teacher	1	2.00%
First-grade teacher	1	2.00%
High School Mathematics Teacher	1	2.00%
HS English Teacher	1	2.00%
Lead Technology Specialist	1	2.00%
Middle School Mathematics Teacher	1	2.00%
Length of Service in years		
1 year	17	34.00%
3 years	10	20.00%
4 years	8	16.00%
No Response	8	16.00%
5 years	6	12.00%
2 years	1	2.00%
Monthly Income		
100,000 and below	6	12.0%
100,001 - 200,000	18	36.0%
200,001 - 300,000	15	30.0%
300,001 and above	1	2.0%
No Response	10	20.0%

Highest Educational Attainment

College Graduate	8	16.0%
with a Master’ Degree unit	23	46.0%
Master’s Degree graduate	11	22.0%
With a Doctorate Degree unit	4	8.0%
Doctorate Degree graduate	4	8.0%

Thus, it implies that the US teachers are female, aged 31–35, and most classify them as teachers. The respondent rendered 1-year service earned between 100,000 – 200,000, with units earned in a master's degree.

The Level of Foreign Language Fluency Anxiety to Filipino Teachers in The United States.

This section represents the level foreign language fluency anxiety to Filipino teachers in the United States in terms of self-perception of language proficiency.

Table 2.0 presents how teachers in the United States see their language skills. The mean results show how much they worry about using English in their classrooms. Starting with the highest mean score and working down to the lowest, it is clear that some teachers worry about how well they speak English. Statements 6 and 7 have the highest mean scores, 3.10 and 3.60 because they show feelings of not being good enough compared to students and coworkers. This shows that many teachers think they could be better than their peers, which could hurt their confidence and make them less effective in the classroom. The participant’s responses during the interviews support the result and imply that teachers must be trained in order to teach and learn in the United States using the English language. They claimed to have dealt with the issue by developing proper speaking skills and self-practice for effective delivery in class. The result is also supported by Namaziandost 2020, which discusses how teachers' inherent capabilities and preparations for English language fluency should be used to determine the success of communication between learners and colleagues. The better their preparations, the more confident they are and the more effectively they communicate.

Table 2.0 The Self-Perception of Language Proficiency of the teacher teaching in United States.

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. I feel embarrassed every time I speak English in front of my students.	1.84	Low Anxiety
2. I think I am not good at speaking English.	2.18	Low Anxiety
3. I feel difficulties in expressing my thoughts.	2.50	Moderate Anxiety
4. I feel pressured when my students ask me unexpected questions.	2.40	Low Anxiety
5. I feel nervous that I will mispronounce the word that I am going to say.	2.60	Moderate Anxiety
6. I think that some of my students speak better English than me.	3.10	High Anxiety
7. I think that some of my colleagues speak better English than me.	3.60	High Anxiety
8. I feel anxious when using English in my class.	2.06	Low Anxiety
9. I am bothered when I have difficulty teaching English cultural content.	2.50	Moderate Anxiety
10. I feel embarrassed when I think that I am not good at English.	2.52	Moderate Anxiety
As a whole	2.53	Moderate Anxiety

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49 (No Anxiety), 1.50 – 2.49 (Low Anxiety), 2.50 – 3.49 (Moderate Anxiety), 3.50 – 4.49 (High Anxiety), 4.50 – 5.00 (Extreme Anxiety)

This section represents the level of foreign language fluency anxiety to Filipino teachers in the United States in terms of Teaching inexperience.

Table 2.1 presents a detailed look at the emotional state of teachers concerning their anxiety levels when teaching in a classroom setting, with the mean scores indicating their varying degrees of anxiety. Starting with the highest mean score and descending to the lowest, it is evident that some teachers experience moderate levels of anxiety during their teaching activities. Statement 2, which expresses the fear of making mistakes while teaching, has the highest mean score of 2.88. This suggests that teachers have concerns about their performance in the classroom, which could affect their teaching effectiveness and self-confidence.

Based on the assertions made by the interview participants, it can be inferred that the beginning of a new class can be a particularly anxiety-inducing experience for educators. This anxiety can affect the initial interactions and rapport-building between teachers and students, which are crucial for creating a positive classroom environment. Consequently, educational institutions should consider implementing orientation and support systems to help teachers navigate these initial moments effectively, ensuring a smoother transition into each new class.

Table 2.1 Teaching inexperience of Language Proficiency of the teacher teaching in United States.

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. I feel nervous when I am about to meet a new group of students.	2.60	Moderate Anxiety
2. I fear making mistakes while I am teaching in the classroom.	2.88	Moderate Anxiety
3. I feel worried before entering the classroom.	2.38	Low Anxiety
4. I feel anxious when I teach in the classroom	2.22	Low Anxiety
5. I feel tense even if I am just standing in front of my students in the classroom.	2.00	Low Anxiety
As a whole	2.42	Low Anxiety

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49 (No Anxiety), 1.50 – 2.49 (Low Anxiety), 2.50 – 3.49 (Moderate Anxiety), 3.50 – 4.49 (High Anxiety), 4.50 – 5.00 (Extreme Anxiety)

This section presents the level of foreign language fluency anxiety to Filipino teachers in the United States in terms of a Lack student's interest. Table 2.2 provides valuable insights into teachers' emotional experiences when confronted with a lack of student interest in their learning tasks.

At the top of the list, Statement 3, which expresses feeling stressed when students do not participate in class discussions, has the highest mean score of 3.38. This indicates that many teachers experience significant stress when their efforts to engage students in classroom discussions are met with limited participation. This finding underscores the importance of fostering a dynamic and inclusive classroom environment to encourage student involvement in discussions. The result is supported by the Key Informant interview results as well as also supported by Kyriacou (2021) on teacher stress, it was found that teacher stress levels are influenced by various classroom factors, including student engagement and behavior. Teachers who perceived their students as less engaged and participative reported higher stress levels. This underscores the relevance of creating an environment that encourages active student involvement.

Table 2.2 Lack of Student Interest

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. I feel discouraged when students lose interest in their learning tasks.	3.36	Moderate Anxiety
2. I feel tense when students are not participating in the performance task.	3.16	Moderate Anxiety
3. I feel stressed when students do not participate in class discussion.	3.38	Moderate Anxiety
4. I feel upset because my students are exhibiting poorly in learning languages.	3.04	Moderate Anxiety
5. I feel disappointed because my students are having difficulty in understanding language.	2.86	Moderate Anxiety
As a whole	3.16	Moderate Anxiety

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49 (No Anxiety), 1.50 – 2.49 (Low Anxiety), 2.50 – 3.49 (Moderate Anxiety), 3.50 – 4.49 (High Anxiety), 4.50 – 5.00 (Extreme Anxiety)

This section represents the level of foreign language fluency anxiety in Filipino teachers in the United States in terms of fear of negative evaluation.

Table 2.3 reveals that the Statement 5 stands out with the highest mean score of 3.56, indicating high anxiety levels. This statement pertains to teachers feeling disappointed due to students' negative behavior. This finding underscores the emotional toll challenging classroom dynamics can have on educators. It suggests that teachers may need additional support and strategies for managing classroom behavior effectively. The result is supported by interview with Teacher D's expression of sadness and disappointment due to negative behaviour in the classroom reflects the

emotional aspect of teaching. Numerous studies (e.g., Sutton & Wheatley, 2003; Sutton & Harper, 2009) have explored teachers' emotional experiences. Negative student behavior can be emotionally taxing for educators who deeply care about their students' well-being and growth. This highlights the importance of supporting teachers' emotional well-being and providing resources for managing classroom challenges

Table 2.3 Fear of Negative Evaluation

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. I feel panicked when my principal observes me during class discussions.	2.98	Moderate Anxiety
2. My mentors' observations make me nervous.	3.00	Moderate Anxiety
3. Students' negative comments about me make me nervous.	2.76	Moderate Anxiety
4. I feel uncomfortable when my principal criticizes me for my teaching style.	2.70	Moderate Anxiety
5. Students' negative behavior makes me feel disappointed.	3.56	High Anxiety
As a whole	3.00	Moderate Anxiety

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49 (No Anxiety), 1.50 – 2.49 (Low Anxiety), 2.50 – 3.49 (Moderate Anxiety), 3.50 – 4.49 (High Anxiety), 4.50 – 5.00 (Extreme Anxiety)

This section represents the level foreign language fluency anxiety of Filipino teachers in the United States in terms of difficulties in time management.

The teacher identifies their level foreign language fluency anxiety in terms of difficulties with time management. According to the results, Statement 1 has the highest mean score of 3.98, indicating high anxiety levels. This statement addresses the tension teachers feel when they are unprepared for class. It highlights the immense pressure teachers may experience when they believe they lack the necessary materials or planning to deliver a successful lesson. This finding underscores the critical importance of effective lesson planning and the need for teachers to feel adequately prepared to teach.

According to the statements of the interview participants, time management is highly challenging in a brand-new environment. They are, however, all positive about taking the challenge and adjusting to the new teaching environment. Teachers, on the other hand, find ways to integrate technology in order to manage more time. It also suggests that a teacher will always find a method to teach students while continuing to accomplish the objective. According to Song (2014), teachers must take steps to appropriately manage time in order to create an effective classroom environment. It is feasible to keep up with the educational demands of every student, solve urgent problems instantly, and prevent falling behind when unexpected occurrences occur by implementing teacher time management tactics.

Table 2.4 Teacher Difficulties with Time Management

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. I feel tense when I am not prepared for class.	3.98	High Anxiety
2. I am nervous when I finish the activities before the class ends.	2.58	Moderate Anxiety
3. I feel panicked when I cannot finish the class on time.	2.52	Moderate Anxiety
4. I feel tense when I am not sure of my ideas for the topic for the class.	3.48	Moderate Anxiety
5. I feel panicked when I cannot finish my assigned task on time.	3.34	Moderate Anxiety
As a whole	3.18	Moderate Anxiety

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49 (No Anxiety), 1.50 – 2.49 (Low Anxiety), 2.50 – 3.49 (Moderate Anxiety), 3.50 – 4.49 (High Anxiety), 4.50 – 5.00 (Extreme Anxiety)

Significant Difference Between Their Level Foreign Language Fluency Anxiety

Table 3 portion shows the significant difference between their level foreign language fluency anxiety when grouped according to age. A One-way ANNOVA was computed to assess the significant differences in the level foreign language fluency anxiety when group according to age. The first variable, self-perception of language proficiency, exhibited a statistically significant difference ($F = 2.68, p\text{-value} = 0.04$). This result implies a meaningful variation in foreign language fluency anxiety among respondents of different age groups. The decision to reject the null hypothesis (H_0)

suggests that age impacts how individuals perceive their language proficiency in relation to their anxiety levels. Consequently, educators and language learning programs must consider age-related factors when addressing and mitigating language anxiety. This could involve tailoring teaching approaches and support mechanisms to different age group's specific needs and anxieties.

The second variable, difficulties with time management, also exhibited a statistically significant difference ($F = 3.26$, $p\text{-value} = 0.02$). This finding indicates that age plays a role in the manifestation of time management difficulties and their association with foreign language fluency anxiety. Rejecting the null hypothesis, in this case, suggests that the relationship between age and time management issues in language learning is worthy of further exploration. Younger and older respondents may experience distinct challenges related to time management, which, in turn, influence their anxiety levels in foreign language settings. Understanding these age-related differences can help educators develop more effective strategies for improving time management skills among language learners of different age groups. Teachers' performance will determine the learning outcomes of the students (Radzuwan et al., 2016). Teachers age with an advanced level of target language proficiency are more competent in managing language teaching and providing substantial support for the learners (Canh & Renandya, 2017).

Table 3.0 Significant difference between levels of foreign language fluency anxiety when grouped according to Age.

Variables	F	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
Self-perception of language proficiency	2.68	0.04	Significant	Reject H_0
Teaching inexperience	1.37	0.26	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H_0
Lack of student interest	1.25	0.30	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H_0
Fear of negative evaluation	2.13	0.09	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H_0
Difficulties with time management	3.26	0.02	Significant	Reject H_0

Table 3.1 portion shows the significant difference between level foreign language fluency anxiety to position. A One-way ANNOVA was computed to assess the significant differences in the level foreign language fluency anxiety when group according to position. The table indicates a noteworthy statistical finding with an F-value of 2.20 and a p-value of 0.03. This outcome suggests that the position held by teachers within the educational system plays a substantial role in shaping their self-perception of language proficiency and, consequently, their foreign language fluency anxiety levels. The rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0) underscores the significance of teacher position in influencing how teachers perceive their language skills.

The implications of this result are pertinent for language education and teacher development. It implies that different teacher positions within the educational hierarchy may yield distinct perceptions of language proficiency, potentially impacting their confidence and anxiety levels when teaching foreign languages. Recognizing this variation can be crucial for designing targeted professional development programs that address teachers' specific concerns and needs in various positions. This result was anchored with Chovancová 2014, that the teacher's position can considerably impact learners' self-perceptions of language competency. The teacher's role, demeanor, and teaching practices can influence how students see their language skills, and this helps them in the learning process.

Table 3.1 Significant difference between levels of foreign language fluency anxiety when grouped according to teacher position.

Variable	F	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
Self-perception of language proficiency	2.20	0.03	Significant	Reject H_0
Teaching inexperience	1.66	0.11	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H_0
Lack of student interest	1.27	0.27	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H_0
Fear of negative evaluation	1.16	0.35	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H_0
Difficulties with time management	1.05	0.44	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H_0
Religion	0.95	0.53	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H_0
Value System	1.24	0.29	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H_0

Table 3.2 section shows the significant difference between level foreign language fluency anxiety when grouped according to length of service. The table presents a statistically significant result, with an F-value of 3.18 and a p-value of 0.02. This outcome indicates that the length of service in the teaching profession has a meaningful impact on the difficulties teachers experience with time management, which, in turn, influences their foreign language

fluency anxiety levels. Rejecting the null hypothesis (H0) underscores the importance of recognizing the connection between length of service and time management challenges among teachers.

The implications of this finding are significant for both teacher professional development and educational institutions. As teachers accumulate more experience, they may face different time management challenges when teaching foreign languages. Understanding these challenges is crucial for designing targeted training and support programs to help teachers develop effective time management strategies, particularly those with longer service records. This finding supports Carr's (2013) study, which found that as teachers acquire more teaching experience, they become more efficient at managing their time. They improve their ability to prioritize activities, manage resources, and plan their schedules. Experienced teachers have a better understanding of how much time certain tasks take, allowing them to arrange their classes and classroom activities more effectively.

Table 3.2 Significant difference between levels of foreign language fluency anxiety when grouped according to length of service

Variables	F	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
Self-perception of language proficiency	1.92	0.13	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H ₀
Teaching inexperience	2.48	0.06	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H ₀
Lack of student interest	2.08	0.10	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H ₀
Fear of negative evaluation	2.55	0.06	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H ₀
Difficulties with time management	3.18	0.02	Significant	Reject H ₀
Religion	1.36	0.27	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H ₀
Value System	1.85	0.14	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H ₀

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study delved into the foreign language fluency anxiety experienced by Filipino teachers in the United States, focusing on their socio-demographic profiles. The findings shed light on the multifaceted challenges faced by these educators in the context of language instruction. Anxiety related to foreign language fluency manifests in various ways among teachers.

Firstly, teachers often grapple with self-perception of language proficiency, expressing fears of making mistakes while teaching and experiencing nervousness when encountering new groups of students. This suggests a need for targeted interventions to boost their confidence and comfort in the language instruction environment. Moreover, teaching inexperience contributes to anxiety, with many teachers feeling stressed when students do not actively participate in class discussions, highlighting the importance of mentorship and support for newer educators.

Additionally, the study revealed that teachers may struggle with student engagement, feeling disappointed due to negative student behavior. Fear of negative evaluation is another source of anxiety, particularly when teachers perceive themselves unprepared for class, emphasizing the significance of professional development and resources to enhance preparedness. The study also identified important correlations between socio-demographic factors and anxiety levels. Age and teacher position significantly influence self-perception of language proficiency, suggesting that tailored support and training programs should consider these variables. Furthermore, length of service impacts language barriers and time management difficulties, underscoring the importance of ongoing support and development opportunities for teachers at different stages of their careers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study. The following recommendations were made:

For U.S Embassy to collaborate with educational institutions to facilitate language programs and resources for immigrant teachers, for the school district principals of the US to prioritize ongoing professional development for their teaching staff, especially those with less experience. Also, these recommend the immigrant teachers to actively seek mentorship from experienced colleagues. A mentor can provide guidance, share effective teaching practices, and offer emotional support to help navigate the challenges of teaching in a foreign language environment. School districts should allocate resources to enhance teacher preparedness and time management. This may involve providing teachers with necessary materials, tools, and lesson planning resources to alleviate anxiety related to difficulties with time management and fear of negative evaluation. Also, educational institutions should consider implementing cultural sensitivity training for international students to help them better understand the challenges immigrant teachers face. For future researchers to consider expanding on this study by examining additional factors contributing to foreign language fluency anxiety among teachers and exploring interventions that can further alleviate these anxieties.

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